

ACHIEVING EDUCATION FOR ALL BY INCLUDING THOSE WITH DISABILITIES AND SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

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Introduction Background

EFA also clearly identified Inclusive Education as one of the key strategies to address issues of marginalization and exclusion. The fundamental principle of EFA is that all children should have the opportunity to learn. The fundamental principle of Inclusive Education is that all children should have the opportunity to learn together. Significant numbers of disabled children and youth are largely excluded from educational opportunities for primary and secondary schooling. Exclusion, poverty and disability are linked. Education is widely recognized as a means to develop human capital, to

ABSTRACT

This article the main problem in the field of disability is the lack of access to education for children and adults with disabilities. This is a very serious issue as education is a fundamental right of all, enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and protected by various international conventions. That in many countries there is a stark difference between the educational opportunities available to children with disabilities and children without disabilities. Failure to achieve the goal of "Education for All" unless a complete turnaround is achieved. In recognition of the widely recognized need for change, the Dakar Framework for Action adopted the World Declaration on Education for All (EFA) in 2000, which affirmed education as a fundamental right and that every setting a new millennium goal to provide for girls and boys. achieving inclusive education. in this, the possibilities of the role of parents and teachers are revealed.

improve economic performance, and to enhance people's capabilities and choices. Exclusion from education can result in a staggering loss of freedom and productivity in the labor market. The international community (at least at the policy level) has recognized education as a fundamental child right and has committed to a framework for action to address this right, and to redress exclusion as directed by EFA 2000.

Inclusive Education in the context of the goals of Education for All is a complex issue, and no coherent approach is evident in the literature. First, at a basic level of policy, unlike

health and labor markets, disability is seen as an array of issues crossing health, education, social welfare, employment sectors, etc. As a result, policy development in relation to individuals with disabilities faces challenges to avoid fragmented, uneven, and difficult-to-access services. Second, Inclusive Education may be implemented at different levels, embrace different goals, and be based on different motives, reflect different classifications of special education needs (SEN), and provide services in different contexts. Specific goals may focus either on improved educational performance and quality of education, or on autonomy, self-determination, proportionality, consumer satisfaction or parental choice. Some of these goals may conflict and produce tensions. Similarly, motives for Inclusive Education may derive from dissatisfaction with the system, from economic or resource allocation concerns, or from a vision of educational reform. Finally, SEN services may be viewed as a continuum of placement options (multi-track approach), as a distinct education system (two-track approach) or as a continuum of services within one placement—the general education school and classroom (one-track approach). All of the variants produced by these different aims, levels, systems and motives may be called Inclusive Education. In order to understand exclusion and strategies for working toward inclusion, it is necessary to examine research on policy and practice at the micro-level (schools and communities), at the meso-level

(educational systems and external agency support services), and at the macro-level (national/international policy and national legislation).

Inclusive Education Practice Lessons from the North. Large-scale cross-national studies in countries of the North provide extensive information on best practice for Inclusive Education. A high priority involves teacher training, perhaps not surprisingly, due to the fact that personnel resources constitute approximately 80% of all school expenditures. All of the studies cited recommend that teacher training focus on enhancing the skills of classroom teachers in areas of pedagogy, curriculum development and adaptation. Training should be intentional and classroom-based, intensive, and on-going in order to promote sustainable effective practice. Second, in priority, is school-as-a-whole reform to support classroom practice. Important factors in whole-school reform include involved leadership, coordination of services, multi-disciplinary planning, parental involvement in decision-making, and in-school support systems to build capacity.

Although a definite trend toward inclusive practice and increase in inclusive education programming is evident in all countries of the North, considerable variation exists, most notably in the areas of classification and placement decisions. In addition, all countries face several challenges. The most significant of these are meeting the needs of SEN students in secondary schools, funding, and resource

constraints. Special issues of accountability are exerting enormous pressures on schools to document effectiveness in terms of outcomes. This emphasis on accountability represents a significant shift from issues of access and quality of services. Systems of evaluation and documentation of effectiveness in terms of outcomes are lacking and need attention. While the studies provide some evidence of positive Inclusive Education effects, gaps in research are most noticeable in this area. Finally, significant gender differences exist that reveal a bias toward boys and were noted as a potentially significant area of concern that was largely omitted in the studies. These lessons from the North constitute a first-wave of Inclusive Education reform in terms of practice.

Inclusive Education Practice: Lessons from the South. In order to describe the dynamics and comprehensiveness of Inclusive Education in the South, this review uses a framework for analysis that includes four domains of inputs, processes, outcomes, and contextual factors in an open-system. An open-system not only accounts for external factors influencing Inclusive Education (e.g., policy, legislation, cultural and socio-economic conditions), but considers these “external” factors as integral components of Inclusive Education development as a whole. This open-system is a particular strength of Inclusive Education in countries of the South.

The most challenging and critical aspects of Inclusive Education

(IE) development in terms of inputs include:

1. Student access, retention and drop-out rates;
 2. Finding, identifying, and encouraging children to go to school;
 3. Poverty and associated characteristics of student background;
 4. Attitudes toward SEN and students with disabilities;
 5. Conditions of teachers' work;
 6. Flexible, adaptive and functional life-skills curriculum relevant to students' lives.
- In terms of process, school climate, collaboration, support, and integrated services/teacher training prove challenging as process domains. Outcomes of Inclusive Education are often illusive and difficult to measure. Student achievement tests of content knowledge provide only one indicator of impact, and are not strongly linked to success in adult life, nor do they provide a measure of creative and analytical problem-solving skills needed for survival. The challenge is to measure success in terms of broad indicators of outcomes and impact. Research suggests that IE programs should look for improvements in terms of contextual factors: individual, family, community, organization, and government. Specific indicators include: presence, participation, choice, respect, knowledge and skills.

Validated Program Approaches and Key Lessons

1. Education goals are often elusive and difficult to measure.
2. Development takes time.
3. Process is often as important as product.

4. Decentralization and autonomy are important tools but not panaceas for solutions.

5. Partnerships and networks are needed at all levels of the system.

6. Integrated and multi-sectoral approaches to learning are essential.

7. Good practices must be carefully analyzed and promoted, and models of good practice must be creatively used.

8. Diversity, not standard solutions to complex problems, must be the norm.

9. Mobilization and advocacy at all levels are essential.

Gaps in the literature encompass:

1. Identification and services of the majority of SEN students who have no visible impairments;

2. Strategies and successful approaches to address access and equity barriers to enrollment and participation;

3. Strategies to address retention of qualified teachers;

4. Data regarding program impact and outcomes;

5. Systematic models to address knowledge transfer;

6. Secondary, tertiary, adult and alternative education programs;

7. Use of technology to support Inclusive Education; and,

8. Attention to social context. This last gap is perhaps the most significant of all, especially considering the numerous social, political and economic context barriers to attendance and participation that have been identified in the literature.

Several critical issues emerge from the IE literature as an opportunity to refocus efforts in Inclusive Education and to improve effective practice. This

review has uncovered four that appear to be compelling:

1. Human rights, 2. Decentralization, 3. Partnerships for change, and 4. Integrated teacher training. Exemplars from several of the 24 'Fast-Track' Countries of the South reveal significant needs in these four areas that also appear to be associated with particular regions. These needs also appear to be associated with emerging strengths that could be capitalized on for future study.

Economic Issues

Financing and support of educational services for students with special needs is a primary concern for all countries, regardless of available resources. Countries of the North are experiencing constraints as well as countries of the South, albeit with vast disparities. In the last decade, countries of the North have experienced widespread economic retrenchment. Tax bases have diminished at the same time that costs have risen dramatically. In these countries, new and expensive medical interventions, combined with expanding social services and welfare benefits, along with an increasing aging population have all

increased pressures on spending—resulting in powerful incentives to control education budgets. At the same time, countries of the South have also been subject to immense pressures – rapid population growth, increasing poverty, war and disease – have destabilized economies and produced strictly limited financial resources. Regardless of relative wealth, education in all countries has

had to compete with other economic priorities such as health care, social welfare, and defense budgets. However, education is widely seen as a means to develop human capital, to improve economic performance, and to enhance individual capabilities and choices in order to enjoy freedoms of citizenship. The strategy of Education for All is driven by a human-rights discourse and clear economic purpose linked to development. Best Practice in Europe and other OECD Countries Turning to European and OECD studies of Inclusive Education, several multi-country studies were conducted between 1994 and 2003. The following subsections highlight some of the major findings from three major studies in terms of best practice, beginning with the earliest studies, and ending with the most recent.

A. The Integration of Disabled Children into Mainstream Education:

Ambitions, Theories and Practices. OECD, Paris, 1994. This survey of twenty-three member countries was conducted to identify common areas of success and difficulty experienced in integrating disabled pupils into ordinary schools. Findings of the study focus on:

1. Placement decisions
2. Parental choice issues
3. Equality of access and integration
4. Forms and models of integration, and
5. Teacher training and staff support.

In terms of placement, a continuum of placements is typical of member countries, from least integrated (special schools) to most integrated (ordinary class placement with

support). Denmark is notable for its 5 principles for making placement decisions. Different kinds of provision for SEN students are guided by the principles of: proximity, minimum intervention, integration, effectiveness and motivation (p.23). Various factors influence placement in all of the countries studied:

- I. Regulations (e.g., Sweden places deaf and severely mentally retarded students in special schools as official policy, whereas national policy in Italy assumes all children will be integrated);
- II. Teacher willingness to accept a child;
- III. Availability of resources; and
- IV. Family social status.

Once placement has been determined, most countries use Individualized Education Program (IEP) Plans to determine academic needs of SEN students. [IEPs are variously called “targeted action programs (Scandinavian countries), “didactic programming” (Italy), personalized intervention programs (Canada)]. In developing IEPs, a positive strength-based approach and needs-based assessments are generally used to determine appropriate curriculum accommodations and adaptations. Effective pedagogical practices such as cooperative learning, peer tutoring, heterogeneous grouping are widely recognized as the most effective.

Finally, in terms of teacher training, a comprehensive approach characterizes best practice: school based in-services combined with “intentional training” (individualized in-class support of teachers), and university courses. One promising trend reported is the conversion of

special schools into resource and training centers, where staff provide outreach support to schools. In France, “zones d’éducation prioritaires” is a well-known example of increased resources to population areas with large numbers of particularly disadvantaged students. Overall, training is a high priority, and the report recommends that the focus should be on problem-solving approaches, as well as training in collaboration and negotiation skills, rather than in specific disability knowledge areas. Member countries also reported higher levels of success in primary versus secondary schooling.

B. Inclusive Education at Work: Students with Disabilities in Mainstream Schools. OECD, Paris. 1999.

OECD carried out this study between 1995 and 1998 in eight countries from three regions (North America, Europe, and the Pacific). A major finding of this study: “From organizational, curriculum and pedagogical perspectives, given certain safeguards, there is no reason to maintain generally segregated provision for disabled students in public education systems” (page 14). In fact, changes in pedagogy and curriculum development were found to benefit all students. The extensive research analyses provided a “substantial if not overwhelming case to support the full integration of disabled children into mainstream schools” (page 22). Also, evidence suggests that Inclusive Education improves performance of non-SEN students, in part because the increased attention to pedagogy and curriculum adaptation generalizes teaching skills to all students. However,

an important caveat to these findings is that close attention has to be given to policy frameworks, parental choice, organization and funding of schools, and teacher/student/family support systems in order for Inclusive Education programming to be effective. Most countries still feel the need to maintain some form of segregated provision—either special classes in regular schools or special schools. (Most frequently cited as needing segregated placement were students with emotional and behavior problems—as schools are reporting a growing number of problems in this area.) Further, in most countries, Inclusive Education programming is limited, but there is a definite trend toward increased Inclusive Education. Several of the top-priority critical factors cited as promoting best practice in Inclusive Education are briefly described below:

Teacher training is accorded a high priority.

Content should be practical (classroom based), focus on teacher attitudes and changes in roles. Good practice is only sustainable with ongoing training (p. 37). Specific skills for teacher training of specialists include:

- working as the special education co-coordinator
- team-teaching
- developing mutual support between teachers and learning to develop effective collaboration through meetings and a problem-solving approach
- the pedagogies of curriculum differentiation

- the development of individual education programs
- the monitoring of progress

With these skills, specialist teachers work with general education teachers in classrooms to serve as a continuing source of development for general education teachers, a practice known as the “enskillling” of teachers. At their best, these support teachers are fully integrated within the school as a whole.

Further, education policies affect training. Policies that support effective training include those that support coordination of services, and multi-disciplinary team planning. Multi-professional training for a coordinated system of services includes specific skills (p. 311):

- knowledge of concepts of inclusion and service coordination at all levels (policy, program, and practice)
- knowledge of the roles of the various disciplines who serve students with SEN
- preparation for functioning as an effective team member (at the service as well as the planning level)
- preparation for co-coordinating services for families

Whole-school approaches

School management personnel need to be closely involved in innovations, especially since they are accountable for school performance as a whole. “Assertive discipline” programs (also known as Positive Behavior Supports in the US) are whole-school approaches to address the increasing violence experienced in schools—an area of “great concern” to member countries. Further, a within-school support strategy is

recommended over external expertise—based on the philosophy that “If a school can handle the sparks, the fire brigade is not required” (p. 39). Characteristics of a within-school support approach include (page 47):

- additional flexibility in the establishment of class sizes and in their composition
- immediate support for regular class teachers from specialist teachers within the school and from assistants
- the reduction of teacher/student and adult/student ratios
- increased skills in curriculum differentiation and the development of more flexible pedagogies through the shared preparation of assessments and writing IEP plans.
- corporate curriculum development, including the making of curriculum materials to meet SEN students’ needs.

Curriculum development

The trend is toward outcome-based curriculum at the primary level and the offering of ‘practicals’ at the secondary level. [In the US, this offering is referred to as work-based learning, and has been found to be the number one indicator of post-school success for SEN students. This 30-country study focused on five areas of Inclusive Education:

- I. Inclusive education policies and practice;
- II. Funding of special needs education;
- III. Teachers and special needs education;
- IV. Information and Communication Technology in Special Needs Education;
- and V. Early Intervention.

In terms of Inclusive Education practices, the findings of this study

reinforce findings of earlier OECD studies in some areas. Specifically, a policy towards Inclusive Education is a general trend. However, special schools still enroll between 1-6% of all pupils in segregated schools and classes.

1. This OECD report notes, that benefits to non-SEN students is an important indicator, but needs more investigation to link costs with outcomes (page 49).

A high correlation exists between the percentage of pupils in segregated educational provision and population density. There appear to be clear disadvantages to segregation in countries with low population density related to cost-effectiveness factors. Major trends in best-practice include:

A. Transforming special schools into resource centers continues to be a common trend. These centers typically provide the following cost-effective supports:

- provide training and courses for teachers and other professionals
- develop and disseminate materials and methods
- support mainstream schools and parents
- provide short-term or part-time help for individual students
- support students in entering the labor market

B. Individualized Education Plans continue to play a major role in programming to determine the degree and type of adaptations needed and to evaluate students' progress. A significant portion of this report focuses on barriers and challenges experienced by European countries as follows:

C. Secondary level education: countries report "serious problems" at this level as compared to primary schooling. Countries attribute these problems to insufficient teacher training, less positive teacher attitudes, an increasing achievement gap between SEN students and their peers, increased academic subject specialization and different school organization.

D. Role of Parents: most countries reported positive attitudes toward Inclusive Education on the part of parents, and that parental pressure towards Inclusive Education is increasing. However, those families that have students with severe disabilities sometimes prefer segregated settings. Also, the trend toward decentralization has led to increased parental power over decision-making.

E. Funding: is cited as a major barrier of Inclusive Education and training. Countries are undergoing major funding reforms. (See the section on SEN Funding of this report for further discussion of this issue.)

F. Legislation: Progress has been achieved, but problems still remain. (See the section on SEN Legislation, 'Section V: Legal Issues' of this review for further discussion of this issue.)

G. Decentralization: There is a clear and widespread trend toward decentralization that plays a key role in Inclusive Education. The shift of resources and decision-making to local authority is seen to increase flexibility, and allow better adaptation to local circumstances. However, disadvantages include wide variations in quality and level of service.

One recurring theme in the literature on Inclusive Education in the North highlights the importance of parental involvement in the education of their children. Most countries of the North have mandated by law, some form of parental participation in decision-making for SEN services involving their children. However, schools still struggle to include parents as partners in Inclusive Education. The issues appear to be complex. For example, some research seems to indicate that level of parental involvement is class and/or race based. Specifically, parents from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds “tend not to participate in or challenge educational decisions pertaining to their children because they feel disengaged and powerless when interacting with school personnel.” Others indicate that the professional bureaucracy of schools carries built in barriers that de facto, exclude parents from meaningful participation. On the other hand, parents who are motivated to get involved, tend to do so based on

dissatisfaction with the school system and to come from majority (white) middle-class or upper class backgrounds. Schools often view these parents as adversaries and tend to blame parents for a student’s learning and behavior problems (Soodak, 1998). The literature on Inclusive Education in the North highlights the importance of parental involvement and suggests several key strategies for best practice. However, there are few systematic models of best practice that would assist schools. The literature is clear, however, that parents are primary stakeholders in the success of Inclusive Education and that more attention needs to be paid to their perspectives, and a commitment made to capitalize on their expertise and to include them in all aspects of inclusive schooling. For most Inclusive Education programs in the United States, research and evaluation on outcomes is largely based on case studies, and qualitative data. However, a few large-scale quantitative studies have been undertaken.

An Input-process-outcome-context framework for Inclusive Education

INPUTS

School

- Curriculum content
- Textbook & learning materials
- Teacher qualifications, training
- Morale & commitment
- Accessible facilities
- Parent/community support
- Braille/Sign Language support
- Action Plans & Needs Assessments
- Evaluation Plan

PROCESS

School Climate

- High expectations / respect
- Guiding Philosophy/Mission
- Participation/choice
- Positive teacher attitude
- Safe and supportive environment
- Flexible curriculum
- Incentives for participation
- Integrated whole-school system
- Collaborative support teams

OUTCOMES

Achievement

- Literacy, Numeracy
- Good citizenship
- Personal development
- Positive attitude towards learning
- Selfdetermination/ advocacy
- Self-esteem
- Social & Independent Living Skills

Attainment

- Formal completion
- Diplomas/qualification
- Preparation for Adult Life

Standards

- Official learning objectives [desired outcomes]
- School-level objectives

Family/Community Characteristic •

- Parental Attitudes/Training
- Household Income
- Economic conditions
- Cultural/religious factors
- Multi-sector coordination & collaboration

Teaching/Learning

- Sufficient learning Time
- Active teaching methods
- Integrated systems for assessment & feedback
- Appropriate class size
- Adapted curriculum to meet individual needs
- Active student participation
- Appropriate supports

Contextual Factors

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Macro-economic and fiscal policies • Political stability, decentralization, • International coordination • Data collection & analysis | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National goals & standards for inclusive ed, • Sources of funding & allocation • Systematic knowledge transfer | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ed. System Management • Parental & Community Participation • Community sensitization & awareness |
|--|--|--|

Summary. Large-scale cross-national studies in countries of the North provide extensive information on best practice for Inclusive Education. A high priority involves teacher training, perhaps not surprisingly, due to the fact that personnel resources constitute approximately 80% of all school expenditures. All of the studies cited recommend that teacher training focus on enskilling classroom teachers in areas of pedagogy, curriculum development and adaptation. Training should be intentional and classroom-based, intensive, and on-going in order to promote sustainable effective practice. Second in priority is school-as-a-whole

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